

Study of Cutaneous Lesions in New Born Babies Born at Maternity and Child Hospital, Government General Hospital, NelloreC Lakshmi Prasanna¹, Shaik Karimulla², P Satya Prakash³, P Nanaji Rao⁴^{1,2,3}Associate Professor, Dept of Pediatrics, ACSR Govt Medical College, Nellore⁴Associate Professor, Dept of Pediatrics, ACSR Govt Medical College, Nellore

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Conflict of interest: Nil

Abstract:

Background: Neonatal dermatoses are the spectrum of cutaneous lesions that arise during the first four weeks of life. The severity of these conditions ranges from physiological transient phases to significant pathogenic entities. Any of these might cause tremendous anxiety for parents, highlighting the significance of a pediatrician being aware of them.

Aim of the study is goal was to assess the prevalence of Cutaneous Lesions in Newborn Babies.

Methodology: This was a Hospital-based observational cross-sectional study done in 1000 neonates born in Maternity and Child Hospital, Government General Hospital, Nellore who could be examined within the first of week of life irrespective of gestational age, sex and mode of delivery. Complete dermatological examination including scalp, hair, nails, palms and soles, genitalia and mucosa of neonates was done to record neonatal dermatoses. Dermatoses were considered as primary outcome variable. Neonatal and Maternal factors was considered as Primary explanatory variable. P value < 0.05 was considered statistically significant.

Results: The prevalence of neonatal dermatoses in our study population was 89.9%. 70.90% had Sebaceous gland hyperplasia, 57.40% had Mongolian spot, 47.80% had Epstein Pearl, 31.00% had Physiological desquamation, 22.90% had Milia, 21.5% had Erythema toxicum Neonatorum, 15.60% had Salmon patch, and lanugo hair was seen in 9.10%. Male babies (93.94%), Low birth weight neonates (94.85%) had higher dermatoses, Mongolian spot and Sacral dimple in preterm babies, Physiological desquamation in term and post term, Milia in term babies, Café au lait spots in post-term babies with significant P- value. Epstein pearl was common in babies to multipara women and milia was common in babies born to primipara women. Sebaceous hyperplasia, Mongolian spot, Physiological desquamation, Milia, Miliaria and Transient Neonatal Pustular Melanosis were commonly seen in babies born through caesarean section. Epstein pearl and sacral dimple were commonly seen in baby born through vaginal delivery. Congenital Melanocytic Nevus was found to be significant in babies born to consanguineous parents. 62.80% of the study population had a combination of fewer than four dermatoses, and 37.20% had a combination of equal or more than four types of dermatoses.

Conclusion: Dermatoses was associated with neonatal factors such as birth weight, gestational age, gender and mode of delivery and maternal factors such as consanguinity, parity, mother's age.

Keywords: Neonatal Dermatoses, Prevalence, Maternal Factors, Skin Lesions.

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Introduction

The skin is the most visible and easily accessible organ of the body. It acts as an infection barrier, protects internal organs, aids in thermoregulation, stores insulating lipids, excretes electrolytes, and provides tactile sensory input. [1]

The neonatal phase is the first four weeks of life of extra uterine life. [2] The change from an aqueous to a dry environment is a significant challenge to a newborn's skin. The skin of a newborn differs physically and functionally from that of an adult. Depending on maturity, cutaneous barrier function, absorption, and temperature regulation differ. The thickness of infant skin is 40-60% that of adult

skin. It has a weaker intercellular bond and produces less sweat. [3] Different dermatological findings in newborns of different racial groups have been recorded in several investigations. Dermal melanosis, for example, is more common in African-Americans, Native Americans, Asians, and Hispanics. Birth markings were found to be more common among Jewish, Israelisthanin, Arab Israelis, according to another study. [3]

According to several publications, the prevalence of Neonatal cutaneous lesions ranges from 57 percent to 99.3 percent worldwide. The skin of "Pre-term babies" (babies born before 37 weeks of preg-

nancy) is significantly thinner and more sensitive to injury; the loss of subcutaneous fat in "Post-term babies" (babies born after 42 weeks of pregnancy) makes them much more vulnerable to heat loss. [2]

Erythema toxicum neonatorum (ETN), miliaria, and physiological desquamation are some of the most frequent benign and temporary lesions seen during the neonatal period; others, such as Mongolian spots and hemangiomas, can endure for months. Although these illnesses are innocuous, they may cause anxiety and concern in parents, prompting them to seek medical help. Other conditions may be pigmentary birth marks, congenital anomalies, cutaneous signs of internal disease, or a pathological condition such as epidermolysis bullosa. [3] As a result, it's critical to recognize the harmless, temporary skin lesions in newborns and distinguish them from more serious illnesses. This will help avoid unneeded therapy for the babies and provide parents peace of mind about the prognosis of these skin manifestations. [4]

Need of the Study: In neonates, cutaneous changes are very prevalent. They range in severity from transitory physiological states to major pathological entities. Any of them could be a source of great concern for parents, emphasizing the importance of pediatricians being aware of them. Correct diagnosis and counselling the parents relieve the anxiety and avoid unnecessary investigation and medication. In India, there are extremely few studies on prevalence of neonatal dermatoses and their association with neonatal and maternal factors. Hence, a study was undertaken on this subject to identify Prevalence of cutaneous lesions in newborn babies born in Maternity and Child Hospital, Government General Hospital, Nellore.

Aim of the study: To study the prevalence of dermatoses in neonates and their association with various neonatal and maternal factors

Objectives are to estimate the prevalence of various dermatoses in the neonates born, to describe the association of dermatoses with neonatal factors like gestational age, sex of baby, birth weight, mode of delivery, maternal factors like mother age, parity, consanguinity in Maternity and Child Hospital, Government General Hospital, Nellore

Patients and Methods: This was a Hospital-based observational cross-sectional study done in Department of Paediatrics, ACSR Government Medical College, Nellore in 1000 Neonates born at MCH, GGH, Nellore who were examined in the first week of life, irrespective of gestational age, sex, and mode of delivery. Parents not willing for the study, Neonates who could not be examined within 7 days of age, Sick neonates on ventilator, Neonates born at other institute and referred to MCH, Nellore were excluded in the study were studied for 6 months period after getting approval from IEC.

Sample size: The sample size was calculated assuming the proportion of Neonatal dermatoses as 94.1% per the study by Poonam Marwah et al. [9] the other parameters considered for sample size calculation were 2% absolute precision and 95% confidence level. The following formula was used for sample size calculation.

$$N = \frac{Z^2 P(1 - P)}{d^2}$$

Z = statistic for a level of confidence level = 1.960
 P = Expected prevalence/proportion of outcome = 0.941
 d = Precision = 0.02,
 Where n = Sample size

The required sample size as per the above-mentioned calculation was 533. To account for non-participation rate of about 30%, another 162 subjects will be added to the sample size. Hence the final required sample size would be 695. During our study period of three months, 1000 cases were included in the final study.

Study procedure: Neonates were examined within 1 week of age born in maternity and child hospital, GGH, Nellore for a period of 6 months from scientific approval. Information about neonates like gestational age, sex, birth weight, mode of delivery was noted. Detailed history regarding age of the mother, antenatal history, parity, history of consanguinity was noted. General physical examination, systemic examination & complete dermatological examination including scalp, hair, nails, palms and soles, genitalia, and mucosa of neonates were done to record. Diagnosis was made based on clinical features.

Statistical Methods: Dermatoses were considered the primary outcome variable. Neonatal and maternal factors were considered as Primary explanatory variable. Descriptive analysis was carried out by mean and standard deviation for quantitative variables and frequency and proportion for categorical variables. Non normally distributed quantitative variables were summarized by the median and interquartile range (IQR). Data was also represented using appropriate diagrams like bar diagrams and pie diagrams.

All Quantitative variables were checked for normal distribution within each category of an explanatory variable by using visual inspection of histograms and normality Q-Q plots. Shapiro-Wilk test was also conducted to assess normal distribution. Shapiro-Wilk test p-value of >0.05 was considered a normal distribution. Categorical outcomes were compared between study groups using the Chi-square test/ Fisher's Exact test (If the overall sample size was <20 or if the expected number in any one of the cells was <5, Fisher's exact test was

used). P value <0.05 was considered statistically significant.

Ethical issues: Before collecting data, all parents will be briefed about the purpose of study and informed written consent will be obtained. Subjects

will be given the right to withdraw consent at any stage.

No monetary or no financial burden to the participant.

Results

Table 1: Distribution various parameters in study population (N=1000)

Parameter	Mean±SD	Median	Minimum	Maximum
Baby Age (in Weeks)	39.02± 1.49	39.00	30.00	43.00
Birth Weight (in Kg)	2.81± 0.46	2.80	1.30	4.50
Mother Age (in Years)	23.19± 3.08	23.00	18.00	35.00

Table 2: Distribution of baby sex in study population (N=1000)

Baby sex	Frequency	Percentage
Female	505	50.5%
Male	495	49.5%

Table 3: Distribution of Maternal factors in study population (N=1000)

Maternal factors	Frequency	Percentage
Parity		
Primi	562	56.20%
Multi	438	43.80%
Mode of Delivery		
Caesarean section	408	40.8%
Normal vaginal delivery	592	59.2%
Consanguinity		
Consanguineous	298	29.8%
Non Consanguineous	702	70.2%

Table 4: Distribution of various Dermatoses observed in the study population (N=1000)

Parameters	Frequency	Percentages
Sebaceous Hyperplasia	709	70.90%
Mongolian Spot	574	57.40%
Epstein Pearl	478	47.80%
Physiological Desquamation	310	31.00%
Milia	229	22.90%
Erythema Toxicum	215	21.50%
Salmon Patch	156	15.60%
Lanugo Hair	91	9.10%
Pustules	42	4.20%
Sacral Dimple	30	3.00%
Congenital Melanocytic Nevus	22	2.20%
Miliaria	20	2.00%
Cutis Marmorata	18	1.80%
Café Au Lait Spot	15	1.50%
Harlequin Color Change	9	0.90%
Transient Neonatal Pustular Melanosis	8	0.80%
CradleCap	8	0.80%
Hemangioma	5	0.50%
Accessory Tragi	2	0.20%
Epidermolysis Bullosa	1	0.10%
Icthyosis	2	0.20%

Table 5: Distribution of others in the study population (N=1000)

Others	Frequency	Percentages
Cleft lip	1	0.10%
Cleft lip & cleft palate	1	0.10%
Natal teeth	1	0.10%
Absent	997	99.70%

Table 6: Prevalence of dermatoses with various neonatal and maternal factors (N=1000)

Parameters	Dermatoses		Chi Square	P Value
	Present	No		
Baby Age Group				
Pre-Term Born (37Weeks) (N=116)	110(94.83%)	6(5.17%)	3.784	0.151
Term Born (37 To 42 Weeks) (N=858)	765(89.16%)	93(10.84)		
Post-Term (>42) (N=26)	24(92.31%)	2(7.69%)		
Baby Sex				
Female (N=505)	434(85.94%)	71(14.06%)	17.614	< 0.001
Male(N=495)	465(93.94%)	30(6.06%)		
Birth Weight				
<2.5 Kg (N=194)	184(94.85%)	10(5.15%)	6.483	0.011
>=2.5Kg (N=806)	715(88.71%)	91(11.29%)		
Mothers Age Group				
<=20 (N=205)	184(89.76%)	21(10.24%)	1.670	0.644
21To25(N=575)	513(89.22%)	62(10.78%)		
26To30(N=196)	179(91.33%)	17(8.67%)		
>30(N=24)	23(95.83%)	1(4.17%)		
Parity				
Multi(N=438)	402(91.78%)	36(8.22%)	3.036	0.081
Primi(N=562)	497(88.43%)	65(11.57%)		
Mode of delivery				
Caesarean Section(N=408)	373(91.42%)	35(8.58%)	1.757	0.185
Normal Vaginal Delivery(N=592)	526(88.85%)	66(11.15%)		
Consanguinity				
Consanguinity(N=298)	275(92.28%)	23(7.72%)	2.652	0.103
Non-Consanguinity(N=702)	624(88.89%)	78(11.11%)		

Table 7: Prevalence of various dermatoses vs baby age (N=1000)

Parameters	Baby Age Group			P value
	Pre-Term born (37 weeks) (N=116)	Term Born (37 to 42 weeks) (N=858)	Post Term (>42 weeks) (N=26)	
Sebaceous Hyperplasia	81(69.83%)	609(70.98%)	19(73.08%)	0.938
Mongolian Spot	80(68.97%)	483(56.29%)	11(42.31%)	0.010
Epstein Pearl	57(49.14%)	409(47.67%)	12(46.15%)	0.943
Physiological Desquamation	13(11.21%)	288(33.57%)	9(34.62%)	<0.001
Milia	16(13.79%)	209(24.36%)	4(15.38%)	0.026
Erythema Toxicum	18(15.52%)	192(22.38%)	5(19.23%)	0.231
Salmon Patch	23(19.83%)	128(14.92%)	5(19.23%)	0.343
Lanugo Hair	83(71.55%)	8(0.93%)	0 (0%)	*
Pustules	3(2.59%)	38(4.43%)	1(3.85%)	0.647
Sacral Dimple	9(7.76%)	20(2.33%)	1(3.85%)	0.005
Congenital Melanocytic Nevus	4(3.45%)	17(1.98%)	1(3.85%)	0.507
Miliaria	3(2.59%)	16(1.86%)	1(3.85%)	0.692
Cutis Marmorata	4(3.45%)	14(1.63%)	0 (0%)	*
Café AuLait Spot	2(1.72%)	11(1.28%)	2(7.69%)	0.029
Harlequin Color Change	5(4.31%)	4(0.47%)	0 (0%)	*
Transient Neonatal Pustular Melanosis	1(0.86%)	7(0.82%)	0 (0%)	*
CradleCap	1(0.86%)	7(0.82%)	0 (0%)	*
Hemangioma	2(1.72%)	3(0.35%)	0 (0%)	*
Accessory Tragi	0 (0%)	2(0.23%)	0 (0%)	*
Icthyosis	0 (0%)	2(0.23%)	0 (0%)	*
Epidermolysis Bullosa	0 (0%)	1(0.12%)	0 (0%)	*

*No statistical test was applied due to 0 subjects in the cells

Table 8: Prevalence of various dermatoses vs baby gender (N=1000)

Parameters	Baby Gender		P value
	Female (N=505)	Male (N=495)	
Sebaceous Hyperplasia	315(62.38%)	394(79.6%)	<0.001
Mongolian Spot	267(52.87%)	307(62.02%)	0.003
Epstein Pearl	250(49.5%)	228(46.06%)	0.276
Physiological Desquamation	122(24.16%)	188(37.98%)	<0.001
Milia	89(17.62%)	140(28.28%)	<0.001
Erythema Toxicum	87(17.23%)	128(25.86%)	<0.001
Salmon Patch	86(17.03%)	70(14.14%)	0.208
Lanugo Hair	43(8.51%)	48(9.7%)	0.516
Pustules	24(4.75%)	18(3.64%)	0.379
Sacral Dimple	13(2.57%)	17(3.43%)	0.425
Congenital Melanocytic Nevus	6(1.19%)	16(3.23%)	0.028
Miliaria	8(1.58%)	12(2.42%)	0.343
Cutis Marmorata	6(1.19%)	12(2.42%)	0.412
Café AuLait Spot	8(1.58%)	7(1.41%)	0.825
Harlequin Color Change	2(0.4%)	7(1.41%)	0.105
Transient Neonatal Pustular Melanosis	3(0.59%)	5(1.01%)	0.502
CradleCap	2(0.4%)	6(1.21%)	0.174
Hemangioma	3(0.59%)	2(0.4%)	1.000
Accessory Tragi	0 (0%)	2(0.4%)	*
Icthyosis	0 (0%)	2(0.4%)	*
Epidermolysis Bullosa	0 (0%)	1(0.2%)	*

*No statistical test was applied due to 0 subjects in the cells

Table 9: Prevalence of various dermatoses vs baby birth weight (N=1000)

Parameters	Baby Birth Weight		P value
	<2.5 Kg (N=194)	≥2.5Kg (N=806)	
Sebaceous Hyperplasia	144(74.23%)	565(70.1%)	0.256
Mongolian Spot	124(63.92%)	450(55.83%)	0.041
Epstein Pearl	90(46.39%)	388(48.14%)	0.662
Physiological Desquamation	53(27.32%)	257(31.89%)	0.217
Milia	33(17.01%)	196(24.32%)	0.030
Erythema Toxicum	35(18.04%)	180(22.33%)	0.191
Salmon Patch	37(19.07%)	119(14.76%)	0.138
Lanugo Hair	64(32.99%)	27(3.35%)	<0.001
Pustules	6(3.09%)	36(4.47%)	0.392
Sacral Dimple	17(8.76%)	13(1.61%)	<0.001
Congenital Melanocytic Nevus	5(2.58%)	17(2.11%)	0.597
Miliaria	2(1.03%)	18(2.23%)	0.397
Cutis Marmorata	5(2.58%)	13(1.61%)	0.368
Café AuLait Spot	2(1.03%)	13(1.61%)	0.748
Harlequin Color Change	5(2.58%)	4(0.5%)	0.017
Transient Neonatal Pustular Melanosis	2(1.03%)	6(0.74%)	0.656
CradleCap	2(1.03%)	6(0.74%)	0.656
Hemangioma	2(1.03%)	3(0.37%)	0.250
Accessory Tragi	1(0.52%)	1(0.12%)	0.351
Icthyosis	1(0.52%)	1(0.12%)	0.351
Epidermolysis Bullosa	0 (0%)	1(0.12%)	*

*No statistical test was applied due to 0 subjects in the cell

Table 10: Prevalence of various dermatoses vs mother's age group (N=1000)

Parameters	Mother's Age Group				P value
	≤ 20 (N=205)	21 to 25 (N=575)	26 to 30 (N=196)	>30 (N=24)	
Sebaceous Hyperplasia	132(64.39%)	417(72.52%)	139 (70.92%)	21(87.5%)	0.043
Mongolian Spot	118(57.56%)	327(56.87%)	113(57.65%)	16(66.67%)	0.821
Epstein Pearl	74(36.1%)	272(47.3%)	115(58.67%)	17(70.83%)	<0.001
Physiological Desquamation	68(33.17%)	180(31.3%)	51(26.02%)	11(45.83%)	0.157
Milia	50(24.39%)	131(22.78%)	45(22.96%)	3(12.5%)	0.630
Erythema Toxicum	36(17.56%)	133(23.13%)	40(20.41%)	6 (25%)	0.376
Salmon Patch	40(19.51%)	88(15.3%)	25(12.76%)	3(12.5%)	0.284
Lanugo Hair	19(9.27%)	45(7.83%)	25(12.76%)	2(8.33%)	0.229
Pustules	6(2.93%)	30(5.22%)	6(3.06%)	0 (0%)	*
Sacral Dimple	6(2.93%)	19(3.3%)	5(2.55%)	0 (0%)	*
Congenital Melanocytic Nevus	6(2.93%)	13(2.26%)	1(0.51%)	2(8.33%)	0.063
Miliaria	5(2.44%)	13(2.26%)	2(1.02%)	0 (0%)	*
Cutis Marmorata	5(2.44%)	10(1.74%)	2(1.02%)	1(4.17%)	0.589
Café AuLait Spot	3(1.46%)	11(1.91%)	1(0.51%)	0 (0%)	0.507
Harlequin Color Change	3(1.46%)	4(0.7%)	0 (0%)	2(8.33%)	*
Transient Neonatal Pustular Melanosis	1(0.49%)	5(0.87%)	2(1.02%)	0 (0%)	*
CradleCap	1(0.49%)	5(0.87%)	2(1.02%)	0 (0%)	*
Hemangioma	2(0.98%)	3(0.52%)	0 (0%)	0 (0%)	*
Accessory Tragi	1(0.49%)	1(0.17%)	0 (0%)	0 (0%)	*
Ichthyosis	0 (0%)	1(0.17%)	1(0.51%)	0 (0%)	*
Epidermolysis Bullosa	0 (0%)	0 (0%)	1(0.51%)	0 (0%)	*

*No statistical test was applied due to 0 subjects in the cell

Table 11: Prevalence of various dermatoses vs parity (N=1000)

Parameters	Parity		P value
	Primi (N=562)	Multi (N=438)	
Sebaceous Hyperplasia	395(70.28%)	314(71.69%)	0.628
Mongolian Spot	322(57.3%)	252(57.53%)	0.940
Epstein Pearl	210(37.37%)	268(61.19%)	<0.001
Physiological Desquamation	170(30.25%)	140(31.96%)	0.561
Milia	149(26.51%)	80(18.26%)	0.002
Erythema Toxicum	114(20.28%)	101(23.06%)	0.289
Salmon Patch	91(16.19%)	65(14.84%)	0.559
Lanugo Hair	45(8.01%)	46(10.5%)	0.173
Pustules	22(3.91%)	20(4.57%)	0.610
Sacral Dimple	22(3.91%)	8(1.83%)	0.055
Congenital Melanocytic Nevus	15(2.67%)	7(1.6%)	0.252
Miliaria	15(2.67%)	5(1.14%)	0.087
Cutis Marmorata	13(2.31%)	5(1.14%)	0.167
Café AuLait Spot	9(1.6%)	6(1.37%)	0.765
Harlequin Color Change	5(0.89%)	4(0.91%)	1.000
Transient Neonatal Pustular Melanosis	4(0.71%)	4(0.91%)	0.735
CradleCap	3(0.53%)	5(1.14%)	0.308
Hemangioma	4(0.71%)	1(0.23%)	0.393
Accessory Tragi	2(0.36%)	0 (0%)	*
Ichthyosis	0 (0%)	2(0.46%)	*
Epidermolysis Bullosa	0 (0%)	1(0.23%)	*

*No statistical test was applied due to 0 subjects in the cell

Table 12: Prevalence of various dermatoses vs mode of delivery (N=1000)

Parameters	Mode of Delivery		P value
	Caesarean Section (N=408)	Normal Vaginal Delivery (N=592)	
Sebaceous Hyperplasia	320(78.43%)	389(65.71%)	<0.001
Mongolian Spot	265(64.95%)	309(52.2%)	<0.001
Epstein Pearl	175(42.89%)	303(51.18%)	0.010
Physiological Desquamation	148(36.27%)	162(27.36%)	0.003
Milia	127(31.13%)	102(17.23%)	<0.001
Erythema Toxicum	100(24.51%)	115(19.43%)	0.054
Salmon Patch	68(16.67%)	88(14.86%)	0.440
Lanugo Hair	31(7.6%)	60(10.14%)	0.170
Pustules	17(4.17%)	25(4.22%)	0.965
Sacral Dimple	7(1.72%)	23(3.89%)	0.048
Congenital Melanocytic Nevus	12(2.94%)	10(1.69%)	0.185
Miliaria	13(3.19%)	7(1.18%)	0.026
Cutis Marmorata	6(1.47%)	12(2.03%)	0.515
Café AuLait Spot	6(1.47%)	9(1.52%)	0.949
Harlequin Color Change	4(0.98%)	5(0.84%)	1.000
Transient Neonatal Pustular Melanosis	7(1.72%)	1(0.17%)	0.009
CradleCap	3(0.74%)	5(0.84%)	1.000
Hemangioma	3(0.74%)	2(0.34%)	0.403
Accessory Tragi	1(0.25%)	1(0.17%)	1.000
Icthyosis	2(0.49%)	0 (0%)	*
Epidermolysis Bullosa	0 (0%)	1(0.17%)	*

*No statistical test was applied due to 0 subjects in the cell

Table 13: Prevalence of various dermatoses vs Consanguinity (N=1000)

Parameters	Consanguinity		P value
	Consanguinity (N=298)	Non Consanguinity (N=702)	
Sebaceous Hyperplasia	215(72.15%)	494(70.37%)	0.571
Mongolian Spot	169(56.71%)	405(57.69%)	0.774
Epstein Pearl	139(46.64%)	339(48.29%)	0.634
Physiological Desquamation	97(32.55%)	213(30.34%)	0.490
Milia	64(21.48%)	165(23.5%)	0.485
Erythema Toxicum	73(24.5%)	142(20.23%)	0.133
Salmon Patch	42(14.09%)	114(16.24%)	0.392
Lanugo Hair	35(11.74%)	56(7.98%)	0.058
Pustules	15(5.03%)	27(3.85%)	0.392
Sacral Dimple	9(3.02%)	21(2.99%)	0.981
Congenital Melanocytic Nevus	14(4.7%)	8(1.14%)	<0.001
Miliaria	8(2.68%)	12(1.71%)	0.314
Cutis Marmorata	3(1.01%)	15(2.14%)	0.219
Café AuLait Spot	5(1.68%)	10(1.42%)	0.779
Harlequin Color Change	5(1.68%)	4(0.57%)	0.136
Transient Neonatal Pustular Melanosis	2(0.67%)	6(0.85%)	1.000
CradleCap	4(1.34%)	4(0.57%)	0.248
Hemangioma	1(0.34%)	4(0.57%)	1.000
Accessory Tragi	2(0.67%)	0 (0%)	*
Icthyosis	2(0.67%)	0 (0%)	*
Epidermolysis Bullosa	1(0.34%)	0 (0%)	*

* No statistical test was applied due to 0 subjects in the cell

Table 14: Distribution of Dermatoses combination in the study population (N=1000)

Dermatoses combination	Frequency	Percentages
0	101	10.10%
1	113	11.30%
2	195	19.50%
3	219	21.90%
4	182	18.20%
5	114	11.40%
6	53	5.30%
7	17	1.70%
8	5	0.50%
9	1	0.10%
Dermatoses		
<4	628	62.80%
>=4	372	37.20%

Discussion

The skin of a newborn is thinner and less hairy than the skin of an adult. The shift from the aqueous intrauterine environment to extrauterine life plays a crucial role.

The newborn's skin quickly adjusts to its environment and may show a range of lesions that might be temporary, physiological, or pathological. To correctly diagnose benign physiological problems and other pathological illnesses like infections or genodermatoses that require appropriate intervention and treatment, early diagnosis and differentiation of these dermatoses is essential. This study considered dermatoses as the primary outcome variable and Neonatal and Maternal factor as a primary explanatory variable.

The present study included 1000 babies for the final analysis with a mean gestational age of the baby was 39.02 ± 1.49 (weeks), ranging between 30 to 43 weeks. There was an early equal distribution of gender among the study population (F: 50.5% vs. M: 49.5%). The mean birthweight of the

study population was 2.81 ± 0.46 (kg), ranging between 1.30 kg to 4.50 kg. The mean maternal age in the study population was 23.19 ± 3.08 (years), ranging from 18 to 35 years. Primiparity was observed in 56.20% and multiparity in 43.80%. Normal vaginal delivery occurred in 59.2% and cesarean section in 40.8% in our study. The history of consanguinity was observed in 29.8% of our study population. Preterm babies were 11.6%, Term babies were 85.8% and post-term babies were 2.6% in our study.

Most newborns were term-born (89%), preterm 9.3%, and post-term 1.6%. Babies born less than 2.50 kgs were 57.5%, and greater than 2.50 kg were 42.4%. There was a history of consanguinity in 44.2% and absent in 55.8%. Vaginal delivery was 68.8%, and C- section in 31.2% occurred in their study. Most mothers were between age 20-30yrs (83.7%); 13.3% were <20yrs, and 3.0% were in the age group >30-35 yrs. Kruger, E et al. [8] study also found vaginal delivery in the majority (74.3%), C -section in 25.7%. Multiparity was found in 62%, and primiparous was found in 38%.

Table 15: Comparing the characteristics of the study population (sample size, gender frequency & mean age of mothers) with different studies

Studies	Study population(n)	Male%/Female%	Mean age of mothers
Haveri, F et al. [4]	1000	54.3%/45.7%	
Krüger, E et al. [8]	350	54.8%/67.4%	24.9±4.9yrs
Present study	1000	M:49.5%/50.5%	23.19±3.08 yrs

Table 16: Comparing parity, consanguinity, and mode of delivery of study population with various studies

Studies	Parity		Consanguinity present	Mode of delivery	
	Multi	Primi		VD	LSCS
Haveri, F et al. [4]	-	-	44.2%	68.8%	31.2%
Krüger, E et al [8]	62%	38%	-	74.3%	25.7%
Present study	43.8%	56.2%	29.8%	59.2%	40.8%

Prevalence of Dermatoses: According to the literature, the prevalence of dermatoses among newborns across different regions varies. In the present study, we found the prevalence of dermatoses in

89.90%. Nearly 62.80% of new borns have <4 combinations of Dermatoses, and 37.20% of newborn have ≥ 4 combinations of Dermatoses. A study

by KrugerE et al. [8] found more than one type of cutaneous development in 84.6% of a new born.

Table 17: Comparing the prevalence of dermatoses among the new-born across various studies to the present study

Studies	Prevalence of ND
Adebisi, H et al. [5]	61.2%
Kanemura, P et al. [7]	80.9%
Krüger, E et al. [8]	94.8%
Marwah, P et al. [9]	94.1%
Present study	89.9%

This study found sebaceous hyperplasia in the majority (70.90%), followed by Mongolian Spot in 57.40%, Epstein Pearl in 47.80%, Physiological Desquamation in 31.00%, Milia in 22.90%, Erythema Toxicum in 21.5% and Salmon Patch in 15.60%. Lesser frequency of cleft lip and palate

and natal teeth was observed among the neonates (0.1% each, respectively). The prevalence of skin lesions is comparable to that of the previous study results, except for sebaceous gland hyperplasia, which has shown the highest prevalence (70.90%) in the present study.

Table 18: Comparing the prevalence of different Dermatoses in the study population with various studies

	Marwah, P et al. [9]	Haveri, F et al. [4]	Chaithirayanon S,et al. [13]	Shehab et al. [1]	Firouzi H, et al. [11]	Present study
Sebaceous hyperplasia	31.7%	89.4%	78%	3%		70.90%
Mongolian Spot	62.9%	84.7%	100%	20.5%	37%	57.4%
Epstein Pearl	48.8%	89.1%	71.3%	-	-	47.8%
Physiological Desquamation	10.7%	10.5%	-	-	21.1%	31%
Milia	40.6%	18.3%	-	5.3%	45.2%	22.9%
Erythema toxicum	41.8%	23.2%	46.5%	-	43%	21.5%
Salmon Patch	0.6%	20.7%	16.6%	3.8%	37.3%	15.6%
Cleft lip & palate	1.1%	0.1%	-	--	-	0.1%
Natal teeth	0.9%	-	-	-	-	0.1%

Association of dermatoses with neonatal factors:

Prevalence of dermatoses across the baby age was insignificant, with a P- value of 0.151. Prevalence of dermatoses between baby gender was found to be significant with a P-the value of <0.001. Prevalence of dermatoses between baby birth weights was found to be significant with a P- the value of 0.011. In contrast to our study findings, studies by Adegbidi H et al. [5], Jain et al. [6], and Sachdeva M et al. [12] found an insignificant association between gender, gestational age, and birth weight with neonatal dermatoses. However, in line with our study, studies by Haveri, F et al. [4], and Shehab et al. [1] found a significant association with neonatal dermatoses. Mongolian spot was seen more in preterm compared to term and post-term babies and it was found to be significant with a P- the value of 0.010. In contrast, Kanumuru P et al. [7] and Sachdeva et al. [12] found Mongolian spots as the most frequent lesion among term babies. Prevalence of physiological desquamation was seen more in term and post-term babies than in preterm babies was found to be significant with a P-the value of <0.001. The study by Kanumuru et al. [7] found more physiological desquamation in term babies, though statistically insignificant. In contrast, Gokdemir G et al. [10] noted desquamation more commonly in pre-terms.

This study found a significant presence of Milia in term babies compared to preterm and post-term baby. A study by Sadana DJ et al. [17] found a significantly more significant proportion ($P = 0.001$) of milia in neonates born at term (70.2%). Similar findings were found in El-Moneim, A et al. [18] and Dash, K et al. [19] studies. Prevalence of sacral dimple was more seen in preterm babies compared to term and post-term babies and it was found to be statistically significant.

This study found a significant presence of Café AuLait Spot in post-term baby compared to preterm and term baby with a P-value of 0.029. There was no statistically significant difference in baby age group with different skin lesions (like Sebaceous Hyperplasia, Epstein Pearl, Erythema Toxicum, Salmon Patch, Pustules, Miliaria, Cutis Marmorata)(P value >0.05).

The dermatoses such as Sebaceous Hyperplasia, milia, physiological desquamation, and Erythema Toxicum were significant among the male babies (P value of <0.001). Congenital melanocytic nevus was significant among the male babies (P-value 0.028). There was no statistically significant difference in baby gender with different skin lesions (like, Epstein Pearl, Salmon Patch, Lanugo Hair, Pustules, Sacral Dimple, Miliaria Cutis Marmorata, CaféAuLait Spot, Harlequin Color Change, Transi-

ent Neonatal Pustular Melanosis, Cradle Cap and Hemangioma) (P value >0.05). In a study by Varghese et al. [2] Mongolian spots were the most prevalent lesion among male babies (46.30 percent). Milia (30.90percent), Miliaria rubra (8.80percent), Epstein pearls (8.10percent), and Erythema toxicum Neonatorum (8.10percent) were the other prevalent lesions found in the male newborns. Further, our study findings were consistent with previous research such as Sachdeva et al. [12]

The Mongolian spot, Lanugo Hair, Sacral Dimple, Harlequin Color Change were more commonly seen in low birth weight babies and it were found to be significant with a P value of <0.05. Milia was the most significant among the normal birth weight neonates (P value of 0.030).

There was no statistically significant difference in baby birth weight with different skin lesions (like sebaceous hyperplasia, Epstein Pearl, physiological desquamation, Erythema Toxicum, Salmon Patch, Pustules, Congenital Melanocytic Nevus, Miliaria, Cutis Marmorata, Café Au Lait Spot, Transient Neonatal Pustular Melanosis, Cradle Cap, Hemangioma, Accessory Tragi and Ichthyosis) (P value >0.05). Analysis by Kanumuru P et al. [7] Sachdeva et al. [12] found that babies weighing more than 2.5kg had the maximum number of cutaneous lesions. Kanemura, P et al. [7] found Lanugo hair was more frequent (66.7%) in babies weighing less than 2.5kg.

Association of dermatoses with maternal factor:

Several types of research have been undertaken to investigate the relationship between dermatoses with various maternal factors. In our study, no statistically significant association could be found between the mothers' age, parity, consanguinity, and dermatoses (p>0.05); similarly, in studies by Adegbedi, H et al. [5], Jain et al. [6], and Sachdeva M et al., [12] found insignificant association of mode of delivery, parity with dermatoses. Sebaceous hyperplasia & Epstein pearl were more common in a baby born to a mother age more than 30yrs of age and it was found to be statistically significant (P value <0.05%). There was no statistically significant difference in mother's age group with different skin lesions (like Mongolian spot, physiological desquamation, Milia, Erythema Toxicum, Salmon Patch, Lanugo Hair, Congenital Melanocytic Nevus, Cutis Marmorata, and Café Au Lait Spot) (P value >0.05). Varghese et al. [2] found Mongolian spots were more prevalent among babies born to mothers under the age of 20 (50.0%) and those born to mothers over the age of 30 yrs (55%).

Prevalence of Epstein pearl between parity was significant with a P-value of <0.001, with the majority of 61.19% of babies born to multipara having Epstein pearl. Prevalence of Milia between parity

was significant with a P-value of 0.002, with the majority of 26.51% of a baby born to primipara having Milia. There was no statistically significant difference in parity with different skin lesions (like sebaceous hyperplasia, Mongolian spot, physiological desquamation, Erythema Toxicum, Salmon Patch, Lanugo Hair, Pustules, Sacral Dimple, Congenital Melanocytic Nevus, Miliaria, Cutis Marmorata, Café Au Lait Spot, Transient Neonatal Pustular Melanosis, Cradle Cap and Hemangioma) (P value >0.05). A study by Sadana DJ et al. [17] found a significant presence of Mongolian spots in neonates born to multiparous women.

Prevalence of sebaceous hyperplasia, Mongolian spot and milia between mode of delivery was found to be significant with a P-value of <0.001, with the majority of babies with sebaceous hyperplasia, Mongolian spot and Milia were born through cesarean section. Prevalence of Epstein pearl, and sacral dimple were found to be more prevalent in babies born through normal vaginal delivery, and it was statistically significant. There was no statistically significant difference in the mode of delivery with different skin lesions (like, Erythema toxicum, Salmon Patch, Lanugo Hair, Pustules, Congenital Melanocytic Nevus, Cutis Marmorata, Café Au Lait Spot, Harlequin Color Change, Cradle Cap, Hemangioma and Accessory Tragi) (P value >0.05). Kanumuru, P et al. [7] studied the presence of Mongolian spots, Epstein pearl, and lanugo hair among neonates was significantly associated with mothers who underwent cesarean section. However, in their study, Sachdeva et al found an association between lanugo hair and vaginal delivery.

In the present study, Congenital Melanocytic Nevus was more common in babies born through Consanguineous parents and it was found to be significant, with a P- value of <0.001. There was no statistically significant difference in Consanguinity with different skin lesions (like sebaceous hyperplasia, Mongolian spot, Epstein Pearl, physiological desquamation, Milia, Erythema Toxicum, Salmon Patch, Lanugo Hair, Pustules, Sacral Dimple, Miliaria, Cutis Marmorata, Café Au Lait Spot, Harlequin Color Change, Cradle Cap and Hemangioma) (P value >0.05).

Conclusion

This study was a cross-sectional study involving 1000 neonates with a prevalence of neonatal dermatoses of 89.9%. Neonates included are of a mean gestational age of 39.02 ± 1.49 weeks with an almost equal gender ratio where the girls were 50.5%, and boys were 49.5%. The average mothers' age in the present study is 23.19 ± 3.08 ranging between 18 to 35 years, and among them, primiparous women being 56.20% and multiparous being 43.80%. The average birth weight of babies ranged between 1.30kg to 4.50kg. In our study, 40.08%

had delivered through cesarean section and 59.2% through vaginal delivery. Consanguinity was noted in 29.8% in our study. The most common neonatal dermatoses found were sebaceous hyperplasia, followed by Mongolian spot, Epstein Pearl, Physiological desquamation, milia, and erythema toxicum neonatorum. Sebaceous hyperplasia was commonly seen in 70.90% of neonates. Mongolian spot was found in 57.40%. Epstein pearl was found in 47.80%. Physiological desquamation was found in 31%. Milia was found in 22.90%. Erythema toxicum was found in 21.50%. Salmon patch was found in only 15.6% of the study population. The prevalence of lanugo hair in our study was 9.10%

The prevalence of dermatoses were more common in male babies compared to female babies and it was found to be statistically significant. The prevalence of dermatoses were more common in low birth weight babies compared to normal birth weight babies and it was found to be statistically significant. Other parameters like baby age, mother age, parity, mode of delivery, consanguinity did not show statistically significant difference.

Mongolian spot was more common in preterm baby compared to term and post term baby and it was found to be statistically significant. Physiological desquamation was more seen in term and post term baby compared to preterm baby and it was found to be statistically significant. Milia was more seen in term baby compared to preterm and postterm babies and it was found to be statistically significant. Sacral dimple was more seen in preterm baby compared to term and post term baby and it was found to be statistically significant. CaféAuLait Spot was more common in post-term baby and it was found to be statistically significant. Other dermatoses like Sebaceous Hyperplasia, Epstein Pearl, Erythema Toxicum, and Salmon Patch, Pustules, Miliaria, and Congenital melanocytic nevus did not show statistically significant difference.

Sebaceous Hyperplasia, Mongolian spot, Physiological desquamation, Milia, Erythema Toxicum, Congenital melanocytic nevus were more common in male babies compared to female babies and it were found to be statistically significant. Other dermatoses like, Epstein Pearl, Salmon Patch, Lanugo Hair, Pustules, Sacral Dimple, Miliaria, Cutis Marmorata, CaféAu Lait Spot, Harlequin Color Change, Transient Neonatal Pustular Melanosis, Cradle Cap and Hemangioma did not show statistically significant difference in their distribution with the respect to baby gender In low birth neonates, Mongolian spots, Lanugo hair, Harlequin color change and sacral dimple were observed more. In contrast, Milia was seen more in normal birth weight babies. Sebaceous hyperplasia and Epstein pearl were more common in babies born to women more than 30 years of age.

Epstein pearl was commonly seen in baby born to multipara women and milia was commonly seen in baby born to primipara women. Sebaceous hyperplasia, Mongolian spot, Physiological desquamation, Milia, Miliaria and Transient Neonatal Pustular Melanosis were commonly seen in babies born through caesarean section. Epstein pearl and sacral dimple were commonly seen in baby born through vaginal delivery. Congenital Melanocytic Nevus was found to be significant in babies born to consanguineous parents. 62.80% of the study population had a combination of fewer than four dermatoses, and 37.20% had a combination of equal or more than 40% of dermatoses.

Limitations: This study did not include other factors such as genetic, environmental, racial, maternal blood group, or regular antenatal checkup, which could have influenced neonatal dermatoses. The study did not mention the location of lesions on neonates. Association of cutaneous lesions to type of maternal disease, smoking status and pregnancy complications like diabetes, hypertension, etc were not studied.

Recommendations: Examining new born skin might reveal typical variations that occur during the neonatal period. It is necessary to differentiate benign transient lesions from pathological cutaneous lesions and be aware that most skin lesions in newborns are temporary and do not need treatment. Further studies are needed to confirm and comprehend these correlations better.

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